

Vitamin E and the risk of pneumonia: the I^2 -statistic

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Supplementary file

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Table S1. Distribution of the pneumonia cases in the six subgroups of Figs 1 and 2 and the calculation of the crude rate ratio

Subgroup	Vitamin E				No vitamin E				Total N	Crude RR (I_E/I_{NoE})
	Cases of pneumonia	N	Pyrs	Rate (I_E) [10^{-3}]	Cases of pneumonia	N	Pyrs	Rate (I_{NoE}) [10^{-3}]		
#1	26	228	1288	20.2	9	240	1372	6.6	468	3.1
#2	22	690	3865	5.7	9	638	3673	2.5	1328	2.3
#3 noBC	80	1495	8449	9.5	49	1527	8730	5.6	3022	1.7
#4	184	6900	39861	4.6	204	6960	40351	5.1	13860	0.9
#5	65	2660	15453	4.2	74	2593	15015	4.9	5253	0.9
#6	14	1118	6567	2.1	43	1098	6279	6.8	2216	0.3
#3 BC *	58	1473	8407	6.9	61	1513	8657	7.0	2986	1.0
All	449	14564	83890	5.4	449	14569	84077	5.3	29133	1.0

* Beta-carotene (BC) participants of subgroup #3 are shown separately. Vitamin E and β -carotene had a significant interaction in group #3, see Ref. 15. Therefore the β -carotene participants of group #3 are not included in the analysis of vitamin E heterogeneity in Figs. 1 to 3.

N, number of participants.

Pyrs, person years of observation.

Table S2. Baseline comparison of Subgroup #1 in Fig 1 by vitamin E administration.

The number of participants and pneumonia cases, and the baseline characteristics of ATBC Study participants who initiated smoking at an early age (≤ 20 yr), and had low body weight (< 60 kg), and vitamin C intake above the median, by vitamin E supplementation.

	vitamin E participants	no-vitamin E participants	Baseline difference in percentages *	
			Difference	95%CI
Participants	228	240		
Person years	1287	1372		
Pneumonia cases	26	9		
Unadjusted RR (95% CI):	3.1 (1.4 to 6.6)			
Adjusted RR (95% CI): **	3.5 (1.6 to 7.6)			
Baseline variables				
Age (y)	59.7	59.3	0.6%	-1.0%, +1.9%
BMI (kg/m ²)	20.3	20.0	1.9%	-0.4%, +3.3%
Cigarettes (1/d)	19.7	19.4	1.1%	-6%, +9%
Age at smoking initiation (y)	17.8	17.5	1.7%	-0.7%, +4%
Duration of smoking (y) ***	40.2	40.7	-1.3%	-5%, +2%
Alcohol intake (g/d)	11.9	14.5	-18%	-40%, +4%
Coffee intake (L/d)	0.600	0.612	-2.0%	-12%, +8%
Employed (%)	43.9	39.6	+12%	-11%, +34%

The table shows the mean values for the baseline variables that were associated with pneumonia risk in the ATBC Study, see Ref. 11.

* Per cent difference compares the vitamin E group baseline with the no-vitamin E group baseline.

*** One participant in the no-vitamin E group had missing data for the duration of smoking; he did not have pneumonia. In the calculation of the Cox model, the mean duration of smoking was imputed to him.

Fig S1. A forest plot for modified Fig. 2, the two “rest” subgroups #4 and #5 are combined

Fig. S2. A forest plot for modified Fig. 3, restricted to no-beta-carotene participants

